

Scenario Guide

KAITEKI Social Value Toolkit

Bernstein MJ and Withycombe Keeler L

About this document

This document conveys, in brief, how to organize an intuitive-logics scenario workshop. The document accompanies a folder set with pre-organized and developed templates to assist workshop organization across all phases (*note, results and post-reporting phase still in development*). The document is loosely organized by major chronological periods, further subdivided by major functional tasks.

Each stage is concluded with a general checklist whose sub-components are not listed, and which it is your responsibility to elaborate based on your specific process and work-style and workshop needs. We encourage you to read through this entire document before beginning your process and making a duplicate version of this document your own, to help familiarize yourself with what you may have to do when.

Use and attribution

If you plan a scenario workshop using this document or associated folder materials, please give due acknowledgement and cite as XXXXX. To add your perspectives if you used this set of resources and have recommendations to pay forward, please email XXXXX and indicate a form of acknowledgment that suits your contribution.

Assumptions and context

This SW Dev. Kit was developed after organizing a U.S.-based workshop, recruiting from among in- and near-network relationships and requiring minimal international travel of attendees. The workshop was full funded; employed a lead facilitator and lead organizer, who had access to a half-time graduate research assistant. Resources were available to transcribe all completed pre-workshop interviews, as well as for dedicated administrative support on travel and on-site logistics (catering, dinners, hotels, etc).

The main purpose of the funded project was to develop scenarios rather than conduct research on the scenario development process; as such, the first version of the SW Dev. Kit does not include any pre-post research templates or associated information. As a final note, a 5-hour/week undergraduate research associate and 10-hour/week graduate research associate were available to support pre-workshop research to explore initial information on key drivers and uncertainties.

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One + year before workshop

Selecting dates and reserving space

If you are hosting your workshop at Arizona State University, or in any place where event space is at a premium, consider booking a space one year in advance. This will entail some degree of uncertainty and schedule coordination with your team, so plan accordingly (e.g., know the best way to get core-team to reserve time on their calendars). Determine how much time you need for the workshop (one day? One and a half? Two? More?). You might consider reserving two sets of dates at the same time, to provide a back-up. Once you reserve a space, know when you need to have a final date selected to be sure you avoid incurring any form of cancellation fee or, worse, loose access to the space.

Closely related to event space is hotel accommodations. If you're hosting the workshop during a time of year when tourism or other activities are likely to render space in high demand, try to get a rough estimate of how many out-of-town participants your budget can accommodate and reserve a room-block at a hotel near by the venue. Again, be sure to know the deadline for incurring any form of cancellation fees. All of this logistical planning also warrants sitting down with your unit's administrative support team to share a friendly heads-up of your event dates and anticipated needs.

Finally, do be sure to have a sense of increasing clarity of the purpose of the workshop. Is the primary focus to generate scenarios? Or is it equal parts scenario generation and research on the process? Having clarity on this will help resolve subsequent planning elements such as IRB submission, participant requirement, form development, etc.

One or two planning meetings may be sufficient to devote to the event at this stage.

One + year checklist

	Date selected in conference with core team
	Event space reserved
	Hotel block reserved
	Cancellation fee dates noted and calendared with reminders
	Workshop primary purpose(s) elaborated
	Notified administration team of event dates and key support needs

Four- to six-months before workshop

File system; administrative support; IRB

By six months out, it is helpful to have the bones of a file storage and sharing system to accommodate the incoming workflow for workshop organizing with multiple administrative and core-team partners. Our team employed Dropbox for most files, and Google drive to service survey and recruitment list needs. Use whichever systems best support the needs of your core

and administrative support teams. This is a useful opportunity to re-connect with your administrative support team to learn about their needs and yours as the workshop date nears.

On the logistics side, if you're based at a university, a major milestone for completion at this stage is to submit your project for review by the institutional review board (IRB) of your university. This is especially the case for the interviews and workshop, as well as any attendant pre-post research you plan to conduct. We found it helpful to use the IRB process as an opportunity to put in some advance thinking about recruitment (e.g., means and email text drafts), interviews (e.g., survey protocol), data processing (e.g., transcription), and consent forms. Be sure you have current certification or completed any required CITI training for human subject research. Most often, your workshop will gain exempt status, however this will depend upon your subject context (e.g., if it were to involve vulnerable population participants).

- See relevant files "0_IRB_Scenario_ProjectNameHere"

Drivers scanning and recruitment goals

During this time period, the main content/planning work falls around the drivers and environment scan and subsequent recruitment plan. With your research support and core team, begin to scope out the key drivers of interest to begin exploring for your research. Consider using the STEEP (social, technical, environmental, economic, political) heuristic to flesh out different areas for exploration. As you search for information on the current state and 10- to 20-year horizons for various STEEP factors, take note of the kinds of expert and stakeholder voices included and excluded from the literature (peer-reviewed, grey, and popular press). Begin to cultivate a list of experts and stakeholders you might contact for interviews.

Hand-in-hand with this research is to more deeply consider who you want represented at your workshop and why. Reflect on your event purpose, the needs of the funder, research focus, and any number of other factors under your consideration. In our case, it we considered diversity of perspectives and divergence, as well as representativeness. We recruited based on academic background, sector, gender, age, cultural, and scenario experience expertise. Certain recruitment goals may be harder to meet than others. Attend to these areas and mobilize your network and peer networks to help supplement your research and recruitment.

- See relevant files "1_Drivers_and_Background_Research" and
- See relevant files "2_Recruitment_for_Scenario_Workshop"

At this stage, our lead organizer and facilitator met approximately bi-weekly, with the lead-organizer keeping a running to-do list of activities necessary to advance progress. Begin to develop your network of student note-takers to recruit and connect with administrative support staff about appropriate compensation possibilities. Try to start avoiding travel obligations that would have you, as lead facilitator or organizer, out of town in the week before or after the event.

Four- to Six-month checklist

<input type="checkbox"/>	CITI / human subjects research certification complete
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	IRB review complete
	Re-connected with administration support staff regarding event and compensation for student-notetakers as possible
	STEEP Drivers Scan in progress
	Recruitment list in development
	Start thinking about student notetakers you can include

Two- to four-months before workshop

Finalizing interview workflow and goals

Depending on your lead time and team capacity, preparatory work will ramp-up significantly in this stage of organizing. The day-to-day tasks of participant invitation, RSVP coordination, timely response to questions, and scheduling and conducting interviews will begin. If you are the lead organizer, begin to temper your expectations about your capacity to do other large-scale efforts related to the project (especially closer to the two-months milestone).

From a content perspective, this is the time in which to advance your plans for the pre-workshop packet for participants—thinking about what will go into the packet and what you need to do in the next two-to-four months to secure this information. Key for this step will be pre-workshop interview questions to help generate the data that will be most conducive to synthesis for the pre-workshop packet you share with participants. Ideally, your research into STEEP drivers will have helped with this process.

Hand-in-hand with interview questions will be your protocol for data capture, and division of labor. In our project, the Lead Facilitator and Lead Organizer together conducted the first quarter of the interviews, with the Lead Facilitator completing the remainder. All interviews were transcribed, and the Lead Organizer took detailed notes during and after each interview to facilitate immediate reflection on key emerging issues related to the material. These real-time reflections proved vital to pre-workshop report synthesis, when time was too short to delve into the interview transcripts (depending on your priority for the workshop, more time or resources may be available to review transcripts). We used ZOOM for our interviews as the recording feature was relatively unobtrusive and effective, and the platform stable.

- *See relevant files "4_Interviews_for_Scenario_Workshop"*
- *See relevant files "7_Reports_PROJECTNAME" > "7_1_Pre_Workshop_Reports_for_participants"*

Establishing recruitment workflow

Logistically, high-touch recruitment will be the other main event of this activity stage, particularly for the Lead Organizer. In our workflow, personalized invitations were sent to participants. Participants to which we had "warm connections" were invited with permission from our network contact; said network contacts often followed up after being cc'd on the original invitation. Initial invitations cc'd the Lead Facilitator and any informed "warm

connections.” In the “2_Recruitment_for_Scenario_Workshop” folder, you will find an example email exchange thread from invitation to interview scheduling. The following flow emerged:

- Invite
 - o If positive response, reply cc’ing administrative team and including relevant information intake questions. Ideally, all of these questions (including links to brief bios, permissions to distribute bios, permission to distribute email contact, allergens, etc.) are in one single form. Adapt this form to your needs. In your first reply, also seek to secure an interview date.
 - o If negative response, ask for referral to alternate attendees and—if relevant for your work—pursue an interview request.
- Schedule
 - o Complete email back-and-forth until you have secured an interview date. Conclude this round of correspondence with a calendar invitation
 - Send reminders for the interview closer to the scheduled time, as needed
- Follow-up after less than 1 week with thanks after each interview, and any promised next steps emerging from the call.

Stewarding the social process

Remember that the process of inviting people to a workshop is a social process and you are potentially building a network of contacts and relationships of high value to your immediate and future work. As such, communicating in a timely and clear and respectful manner is vital. In addition, practice good “list hygiene”: in the absence of a robust CRM software, use your excel sheet “Recruitment_list_XXXX” with regular zeal, updating entries after each correspondence. The extra 1-2 minutes logging each change in correspondence status or interview status will be well worth it when it comes time, later to have to generate reports, lists, or track guests for final holes in your participant recruitment needs.

Also, on the logistics side of this stage, be sure to stay in contact with your administrative support on the participant data intake process, RSVP survey, travel, and catering logistics. Get them the information they need to help you make the process of organizing as smooth as possible.

- See relevant files “3_Workshop_event_logistics”

At this stage the facilitation/organizing team met approximately bi-weekly, with the lead-organizer keeping a running to-do list of activities necessary to advance progress. Having a sense of who to turn to for final notetaker recruitment is helpful.

Two- to Four-month checklist

	Recruitment list mostly completed; updated regularly
	Administrative support brought fully into the loop
	Catering any other logistics finalized
	Interview workflow finalized
	STEEP Drivers scan completed

	Student note takers AND table facilitators tapped or identified
	Interviews in process
	Diligent, respectful, timely responses to growing list of confirmed participants

One- to two-months before workshop

Final throes of recruitment and self-care

This stage of organizing will often be the most intense, with preparatory work consisting of fielding day-to-day participant invitation, RSVP coordination, timely responses to incoming questions, and scheduling and conducting interviews. Scheduling interviews and conducting them will comprise a an especially large portion of time. Flexibility, patience, and your spreadsheet and note-taking hygiene will be especially important to maintain in this period (in addition to sleep and non-work routines that restore your energy and stamina). If you are the lead organizer, practice good self-care and continue to manage your expectations about your capacity to do other large-scale efforts related to the project.

For participant recruitment, this phase will consist of pulling in last-minute attendees, opportunistic invitations, and strategic asks to fill participation holes based on your particular workshop needs/goals. Continue to implement the process and practices established in earlier periods. Similarly, for participant interviews, implement the note-taking, and post-processing activities you established in the prior period and carry these forward with consistency and discipline.

Sticking with the interview workflow

A helpful rule-of-thumb we developed for interviews was to allow yourself 15-minutes before the interview to prepare your mental state; 45-minutes for the interview (aiming for 30-minutes); and 30 – 45 minutes for post-processing. Preparation will include pulling up the interview questions, consent form, checking the ZOOM meeting room, or other call devices. Post-processing will include labelling the recording file; uploading the recording for transcription; logging the completed activity in your recruitment spreadsheet; typing/processing “detailed notes” (we took notes by hand and then used the process of typing them up to ensure post-interview review); and entering “top line notes.” The “top line notes” reflect what appeared to be most highly relevant content to the purpose of the workshop. Having these clearly distilled immediately after each interview proved vital to pre-workshop participant packet development.

While you conduct interviews, depending on your content and questions, interviewees may be flagging particular readings, case studies and other items that will be resources for you and attending participants. Keep a running list of these and consider having your uGRA or GRA support you in tracking down further details for these resources (*see “Resource List_PRJOECTNAME” in the 7_1_Pre_Workshop file*).

Staying on-top of organizing logistics

A key organizing step at this phase of work will be to reach out again to your administrative support and larger core research team to communicate needs for in-workshop support. For the administration team, this may include name tags, tents; parking validation; staffing for day of etc. **Use this opportunity, especially toward the end of the period, to collect allergen and other key participant information and pass this along to relevant parties (e.g., caterer).** For your team, this will include who crafts the agenda and facilitator guide, note-taker guide, participatory activities/hand-outs, in-workshop slides, performs table facilitation, performs notetaking duties.

Finally, by the end of this stage, aim to complete your pre-workshop report for participants (see for example: *FASE 2020_preWorkshop Packet_nonames in the "7_1_Pre_Workshop_Reports_for_participants" folder*). In our workshop pre-report, we opened with a letter of introduction to the workshop, clarifying your expectations of the workshop and for participants to think about, what's in the packet, etc. etc.; your synthesis from the interviews; workshop agenda; key location information; participant list (if permissions given) with bios (if permissions given); additional resources; workshop consent form, for reference).

Preparing the pre-workshop packet analysis

The way you conduct your analysis for this packet will be contingent upon your workshop goals, lead-time, person conducting the analysis, and purpose of the synthesis (among other factors). In our case, the purpose was to raise key open questions which might prompt creative and divergent thinking during the workshop. We prefaced this synthesis with the following: *"We distilled and synthesized eight thematic provocations from pre-workshop interviews. In considering the future, we open a contested space where individual and collective interests, social and technical inertias, and dreams and ideals are interconnected. The nature of these interconnections may range from harmonies to contradictions, or tangential coexistence. Not all of these aspects of the future can, should, or will be resolved through our scenario workshop. However, in giving these subjects due consideration, our hope is that the scenarios we create together will better prepare us for the complex and uncertain times to come."*

Especially by the final weeks of this stage, the facilitation/organizing team met approximately once per week, with the lead-organizer keeping a running to-do list of activities necessary to advance progress. With about 6 – 8 weeks before your event, it may be useful to schedule a pre-workshop briefing with table facilitators and note takers and core team members, as well as a post-event debriefing. Finally, about 4 weeks, it can be helpful to have secured and briefed the notetakers you aim to have at the workshop.

One- to Two-month checklist

	Recruitment completed; recruitment sheet updated regularly
	Administrative support brought fully into the loop
	Catering any other logistics informed of allergens
	Interviews completed

	Resource list investigated by research support teammates
	Interview analysis completed
	Student note takers AND table facilitators confirmed
	Pre-workshop participant packet near completion
	Diligent, respectful, timely responses to participants
	Confirm hotel and catering and event space to avoid any cancellation fees
	Pre-workshop briefing and debriefing meetings scheduled with core team
	Pre-workshop notetaker briefing completed
	Confirm with event space that you have early-morning room access or night-before access to set-up
	Schedule a day-before or at least week-of walk-through of event space and communicate anticipated table / set-up requirements.

One- to two-weeks before workshop

Sending the pre-workshop packet

Ideally with two weeks to go, you have finalized the pre-workshop packet and distributed this with a cordial, excited email to all registered participants. You are ready to trouble-shoot any final logistical challenges, and in the meantime finalizing the in-room assets you will need to run a successful workshop. These assets include any facilitation, note-taking support, activity guide, table material, guiding slides, etc. etc. A useful resource here to have and adapt for your purpose is the “*Event_day_print_and_punch_list_TEMPLATE*” in the file “*3_Workshop_event_logistics*”.

For the guiding slides, it’s very helpful to talk these through once in advance as a lead facilitator and lead organizer team. You may consider having a short session during the event in which interview findings are reported—prepare this material based on your pre-workshop packet efforts.

Table assignments and event logistics

During this period, finalize your table assignments, keeping in mind any distributional considerations in how participants are placed around the room. Some things to consider:

- If you know of strong personalities you invited, it can be helpful to match with strong table facilitators;
- It can also be helpful to have a well-rounded diversity of experts related to your event subject-matter at each table,
- Also of help will be placing persons with some scenario crafting experience at each table (or having at least participated in one event beforehand).
- Balance of any other factors important to consider at each table.
- Be mentally and emotionally ready to adapt your tables the day of the workshop, as some people may inevitably and out of your control cancel at the last minute.

On the logistics side, begin to assemble the resource boxes that you'll transport to the event, including facilitation materials, printouts, etc. Field any final recruitment issues and see to it that your administrative support team is in communication with all vendors and service providers to share updated numbers of participants, allergens, and in-workshop breakfast, break, lunch, and dinner times.

Hold your Pre-workshop briefing meeting with core team members the week before the event, going through key facilitation needs and concerns; workshop goals; key activities; and any other items of central import to your process and project.

At this point, you will have or soon completed your room walkthrough, double-confirming any audio-visual, table, and other venue-related concerns.

One- to Two-week checklist

	Recruitment completed; recruitment sheet finalized
	Administrative support brought fully into the loop
	Catering any other logistics informed of updates and allergens
	Pre-workshop participant packet completed and sent
	Facilitation materials completed and ready to transport
	Student notetakers AND table facilitators double-confirmed
	Pre-workshop briefing completed
	Actively using revised "Event_day_print_and_punch_list_TEMPLATE" list to track final preparations

Workshop implementation

Showtime

By this time, all of the effort put into organizing the workshop comes to a head and the Lead Facilitator is the star of the show. The facilitator should have all resources needed at their disposal, and the support of the organizer, administrative team, and vendor services, to execute a successful event. Get two good-night-rests in the lead-up to the workshop.

The day before the event, you'll have completed your walkthrough, advising the on-sit vendor of table requirements, and collaborating with your administrative support staff on where and how to place signage to direct participants to the event. You will have sent a final pre-event reminder to attendees, noting any particular details of importance. You have all of your materials for the event on-site, a completed punch list, and a good attitude ready to go.

A final note: having someone to welcome people into the building can be a nice touch.

Things will go wrong: choose your response

Inevitably, participants will come down with an illness; a table facilitator or notetaker may bail; a flight may get cancelled, etc. etc. These events, while unfortunate, are completely out of your control. Breathe. You've done the work. The most important step now is forward with a calm demeanor and smile. Deploy your organizer and administrative support assets as needed to insulate the Lead Facilitator from cognitive burden related to logistics—re-assure and assist where possible; move-on where not.

Disposition and presence

Present with an authoritative, passionate disposition. You care about the work; you're interested in the subject matter; you enjoy the process; you're irrepressibly curious to learn what the people you've assembled today have to share about the topic. Encourage participants to treat each other with respect, help each other along the process, be constructive, respect the perspectives present in the room. Remember, the scenario creation process is not about prediction or judging the quality of ideas. If you make a presentation, stand still and speak clearly when offering the outline and structure of the day. Present with the same poise, authority, passion, and enthusiasm for any content. Use scheduled breaks to re-connect with your team, take moments for deep breaths, or enjoy chatting with participants.

Stay organized

Going into the event, have advised note-takers and table facilitators of how you want them to:

- photograph table-generated materials
- collect and catalogue table-generated materials

Baring major circumstances that you have to monitor, stay off of email and cell-phone during the event to be fully present (especially if the lead organizer is also a participant).

Before you strike the room, be sure all information and data are captured in a way that you can easily reconstruct after the event. Transport all data back to your office and upload relevant photos (to be named later) to your file system.

- folder "6_Results_ProjectName"

Implementation checklist

	Final pre-event walk-through completed
	Administrative support team present at walk through
	Catering and any other logistics teams informed of updates and allergens
	Completed "Event_day_print_and_punch_list_TEMPLATE" list to track final preparations
	Administrative support team present at walk through
	Two good nights' rest in advance of the workshop / self-care
	Show-up early on set-up the day of the event
	Choose patience and grace in the face of SNAFUs and FUBARs out of your control (and in your control)

Post-workshop: immediate aftermath and first three weeks

Congratulations!

We hope you enjoyed the event and can consider it to have been a success for your purposes. Take the next day or two easy and recuperate and honor the success (ideally over a weekend!).

Thank the people (remember, it's a social process)

In the immediate aftermath, back at the office, send out thank you notes, electronic or, possibly hand-written to:

- administrative support team (e.g., good use of hand-written)
- core research team
- workshop participants
- attending funders
- other people with whom you said you would follow up or whom may have thanked you for your effort after the event

Included in this thank you note, insert any post-event experience survey, with questions adapted to your needs.

Data processing

Now that you've got your feet back on the ground after the event, begin to prepare your data for processing in the forms relevant to your post-workshop report(s). This will mainly consist of labelling different photographs of data (e.g., indicating day, table, relevant session, etc. etc.). You or your research support teammates will begin to transcribe photographed data for the report(s) contents. These data will likely depend on the final format of your workshop event.

Event debrief

Meet with your team and talk through how the event went. Debrief the process; reflect on emergent outcomes like relationships, connections, publications, proposals, scenario ideas, etc.

Pay it forward

Please share any organization or facilitation items that came to light while using this guide and help improve the scenario guide.

Future sections:

- Finish drafting the scenarios, either solo, with writers, and with participant validation
- Develop a final workshop report
- Engage clients or key stakeholders on using the scenarios in practice
- Contribute the work to the broader academic and practitioner communities either through presentations or publications